

STATEMENT FROM “TOWARDS THE 2030 GOALS: BEST PRACTICES IN CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR OCEAN CHALLENGES”

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2021 United Nations Decade
2030 of Ocean Science
for Sustainable Development

A CALL FOR ACTION: OCEAN DECADE

The ocean covers more than 70% of the planet's surface and plays a critical role in maintaining life on Earth and our current society, performing functions as important as nurturing an unimaginable biological diversity, generating more than half of the planet's oxygen, absorbing more than 30% of anthropogenic CO₂, or providing us with countless natural, energy, recreational, and cultural resources.

Some ocean ecosystem services according to the First World Ocean Assessment (WOA I).

Notwithstanding that, throughout history, it has not only gone unnoticed in discussions and political decision-making processes but has also been subjected to significant pressures such as climate change, pollution, maritime transport, overexploitation of natural resources, or loss and reduction of habitats.

Unfortunately, regardless of the actions taken in recent decades, the First World Ocean Assessment found that much of the oceans are already severely degraded, and despite the need for a good scientific understanding to reverse their deteriorating health, ocean sciences represent only between 0.04-4% of total research and development expenditure worldwide.

0,04-4%

PERCENTAGE OF TOTAL RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT
SPENDING WORLDWIDE DEVOTED TO OCEAN SCIENCES

A CALL FOR ACTION: OCEAN DECADE

In response to this call for global and urgent action and with the aim of creating a global alliance to address the degradation of marine ecosystems and prevent the loss of ecosystem services, in 2017, the United Nations General Assembly proclaimed the **UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030)** under the slogan **“The Science We Need for the Ocean We Want”**.

This initiative aims to provide a unifying framework within the UN system so that countries can achieve all their Ocean-related priorities of the 2030 Agenda, as well as increasing investment in priority areas where urgent action is required, fostering the necessary international cooperation for the development of interdisciplinary scientific research and the application of innovative technologies that can link ocean sciences with society's needs.

Thus, the **Ocean Decade** will carry out a participatory and transformative process in which scientists, policymakers, administrators, and service users can collaborate and exchange knowledge and practices to meet the decade's **ten challenges**:

Challenge 1
Understand and beat marine pollution
Understand and map land and sea-based sources of pollutants and contaminants and their potential impacts on human health and ocean ecosystems and develop solutions to remove or mitigate them.

Challenge 3
Sustainably feed the global population
Generate knowledge, support innovation, and develop solutions to optimise the role of the ocean in sustainably feeding the world's population under changing environmental, social and climate conditions.

Challenge 5
Unlock ocean-based solutions to climate change
Enhance understanding of the ocean-climate nexus and generate knowledge and solutions to mitigate, adapt and build resilience to the effects of climate change across all geographies and at all scales, and to improve services including predictions for the ocean, climate and weather.

Challenge 7
Expand the Global Ocean Observing System
Ensure a sustainable ocean observing system across all ocean basins that delivers accessible, timely, and actionable data and information to all users.

Challenge 9
Skills, knowledge and technology for all
Ensure comprehensive capacity development and equitable access to data, information, knowledge and technology across all aspects of ocean science and for all stakeholders.

Challenge 2
Protect and restore ecosystems and biodiversity
Understand the effects of multiple stressors on ocean ecosystems, and develop solutions to monitor, protect, manage and restore ecosystems and their biodiversity under changing environmental, social and climate conditions.

Challenge 4
Develop a sustainable and equitable ocean economy
Generate knowledge, support innovation, and develop solutions for equitable and sustainable development of the ocean economy under changing environmental, social and climate conditions.

Challenge 6
Increase community resilience to ocean hazards
Enhance multi-hazard early warning services for all geophysical, ecological, biological, weather, climate and anthropogenic related ocean and coastal hazards, and mainstream community preparedness and resilience.

Challenge 8
Create a digital representation of the ocean
Through multi-stakeholder collaboration, develop a comprehensive digital representation of the ocean, including a dynamic ocean map, which provides free and open access for exploring, discovering, and visualizing past, current, and future ocean conditions in a manner relevant to diverse stakeholders.

Challenge 10
Change humanity's relationship with the ocean
Ensure that the multiple values and services of the ocean for human wellbeing, culture, and sustainable development are widely understood, and identify and overcome barriers to behaviour change required for a step change in humanity's relationship with the ocean.

The 10 challenges of the Ocean Decade for a collective impact.

A CALL FOR ACTION: OCEAN DECADE

And thus achieve **seven goals**:

A clean ocean

where sources of pollution are identified and reduced or removed.

A healthy and resilient ocean

where marine ecosystems are understood, protected, restored and managed.

A productive ocean

supporting sustainable food supply and a sustainable ocean economy.

A predicted ocean

where society understands and can respond to changing ocean conditions.

A safe ocean

where life and livelihoods are protected from ocean-related hazards.

An accessible ocean

with open and equitable access to data, information and technology and innovation.

An inspiring and engaging ocean

where society understands and values the ocean in relation to human wellbeing and sustainable development.

The 7 Ocean Decade outcomes that describe "The Ocean We Want".

One of the essential concepts for carrying out this transformation, as well as attaining sustainable development, is citizen science;

A SCIENCE THAT ESTABLISHES A CONNECTION BETWEEN CITIZENS AND OCEANS THROUGH A COLLABORATIVE APPROACH IN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH INVOLVING ACTIVE PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

Citizen science, along with other new sources of data such as remote sensing and mobile phone records, offers a novel solution to complement and enhance official statistics, and to provide more detailed information that cannot be captured through traditional sources of data such as household surveys, allowing us to have better monitoring of the degree of compliance with many of the SDGs.

THE EVENT

With the aim of promoting and supporting new participatory technologies, on April 8th aligned with UNESCO's Ocean Decade Challenge No. 10, the satellite event **Towards the 2030 goals: best practices in citizen science for ocean challenges** took place at the Barcelona Maritime Museum's auditorium.

Organised by Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, Posidonia Green Project, University of New South Wales and University of Cádiz, four citizen science projects were presented with the aim of disseminating information about the projects and attracting new users, hence the targeted audience was the general public, which allowed the attendance to anyone interested in a healthier ocean just with a previous registration.

The speakers who hosted the event were: Dr. Joaquim Garrabou and Paula López-Sendino (Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, Observadores del Mar), Edoardo Brodasca (executive director of Posidonia Green Projecte, WaterSports4Action), Xavier Salvador Costa and Carlos Rodero García (technical personnel and postdoc researcher respectively at the Institute of Marine Sciences - CSIC, MINKA), Sebastiasn Jara Bunster (I & T expert at Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable), Dr. Mitchell Dean Harley (University of New South Wales Sydney, CoastSnap) and Dr. Javier Benavente González.

Event hosts Towards the 2030 Goals: best practices in citizen science for ocean challenges.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

Observadores del Mar is a citizen science platform dedicated to quantifying a wide range of indicators related to the conservation status of marine habitats and species.

Its primary aim is to support science-based decisions that contribute to the preservation of marine ecosystems, in harmony with UNESCO's Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 14 (Life Below Water) and Goal 15 (Life on Land).

Established in 2012 by the Institut de Ciències del Mar of Barcelona - CSIC), Observadores del Mar quickly gained support as a leading marine citizen science platform from major CSIC marine institutes. Currently, the Observadores del Mar community boasts over 6000 volunteers, 100 scientists, and more than 500 collaborating entities.

The platform collects the data by launching challenges, such as measuring the distribution and abundance of common, rare or invasive marine species, tracking specific species that may be affected by climate change or tracking species that may serve as indicators of other environmental disturbances.

For instance, only during the challenge “Coralligenous weekends” devoted to assess the impacts of climate change in the high-diverse coralligenous habitats dominated by gorgonians in the Catalan coast, more than 70 populations accounting for more than 10000 gorgonian colonies were assessed and the results indicated a severe impact of marine heatwaves in this area.

All the contributed data is publicly available on their website and it's noted into a worldwide map, specifying the location and findings from the research.

Classification template for coralligenous habitats.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

Surfstainable is an open-source initiative platform, focused on continuous data collection related to ocean health. Their aim is to reach coastlines worldwide and contribute in the research for ocean data, creating a repository of scientific figures, eco-friendly products and innovative experiments. It's related to SDG 14 (Life below water) and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Their current project is focused on establishing an open-source framework to gather data and information about coastlines, using advanced technology tools which are adaptable to surfboards. The device will periodically measure temperature and pH while people are surfing and it will be storing the information alongside geolocation coordinates and timestamps on to a data repository server.

The project has been developed in collaboration with sustainability-focused entities such as Posidonia Green Project, the Galician Ecological surf company ERTHA Surfboards, and the new communication lab Slow Future.

MIRA tool's hardware.

MIRA tool.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

MINKA

Minka is a participatory citizen observatory focussed on biodiversity observations. Founded in 2020 by the Institut de Ciències del Mar of Barcelona - CSIC), it is related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) of Unesco, especially with the 14 (Life below water) the 15 (life on land) and 17 (Partnerships for the goals) despite they are on the way to addressing more SDGs by adding to their app and web the possibility to report also environmental data observations such as temperature, air pollution and water temperature.

The observations need to pass a validation process conducted by data curators or expert users from the community (at least $\frac{2}{3}$ of it) to ensure that all the biodiversity observed is identified correctly and the observatory can be used by the scientific community.

The MINKA team is also working on developing homemade devices designed to collect water transparency data, with potential applications in activities such as diving, paddle surfing, and kayaking. This data collection is expected to be included in the BioMARató activities along the coast of Catalonia, to collect biodiversity data together with environmental data. MINKA currently has 1.726 participants, 246.228 observations and 2017 active projects. Last BioMARató in Catalonia, citizens detected 34 invasive species, 40 protected species, and the unprecedented presence of the west African fiddler crab on the Catalan coast.

DIY device: KduSTICK to measure water transparency.

DIY device: KduPro for monitoring water transparency.

CITIZEN SCIENCE PROJECTS

Founded in 2017, CoastSnap is a global citizen science project founded as a pilot project between the UNSW Water Research Laboratory and the NSW Department of Planning, Industry and Environment. It is based on a low-cost community beach monitoring technology that allows citizens to track how the coast, dynamic and resilient, is changing over time: photogrammetry, a computer technique that turns a picture into valuable coastal data using elevation models and ground control points. All the information gathered throughout time will be used by scientists to forecast how coastlines might change in the coming decades.

It can be easily related to the Sustainable Development Goal 14 and the only requirement to use their app (in order to be a part of the project) is to always take the picture from the same location as, otherwise, the data provided will not be useful for future scientific studies.

Stainless steel phone cradle and instructional sign.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

During the satellite event, the four projects —Surfstainable, MINKA, Observadores del Mar, and CoastSnap— underscored key points aligning with the Mission and Vision of the Ocean Decade and the Vision 2030 White Papers:

- **Citizen Science** is an important tool supporting the **SDGs achievements** as well as the ten challenges of the Ocean Decade, particularly CH7, CH8 and CH10.
- The incorporation of do-it-yourself **(DIY) methodologies** and **new technologies** associated with citizen science enables the participation of all individuals in data collection, thereby enhancing our understanding of the ocean and its phenomena.
- Citizen Science is the instrument for **ensuring that no one is left behind**.
- Citizen Science plays an essential role in **supporting evidence-based policy**, enabling citizens to gain a **deeper understanding of the decision-making process** and the needs that inform it.

In light of these insights, the four projects recommend;

- The inclusion of Citizen Science as a key element in the framework of the Ocean Decade.
- The use of Citizen Science as an instrument to:
 - Enhance our understanding of the ocean.
 - Support the development of a Digital Twin of the Ocean.
 - Engage citizens and streamline decision-making processes.

CONTRIBUTORS

- Vanessa Sarah Salvo, Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, MINKA & Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable
- Joaquim Garrabou, Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, Observadores del Mar
- Paula López-Sendino, Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, Observadores del Mar
- Edoardo Brodasca, executive director of Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable
- Sebastian Jara Bunster, I & T expert at Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable
- Mitchell Dean Harley, University of New South Wales Sydney, CoastSnap
- Javier Benavente González, University of Cadiz, CoastSnap
- Xavier Salvador Costa, Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, MINKA
- Carlos Rodero García, Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, MINKA
- Jaume Piera, Institut de Ciències del Mar - CSIC, MINKA
- Mireia Vega Herrera, Universitat de Barcelona, Aprenentatge Servei (ApS) de Desenvolupament Sostenible, Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable
- Noa García Battersby, Universitat de Barcelona, Aprenentatge Servei (ApS) de Desenvolupament Sostenible, Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable
- Artur Masforroll Almeda, Universitat de Barcelona, Aprenentatge Servei (ApS) de Desenvolupament Sostenible, Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable
- Aida Bustos Giménez, Universitat de Barcelona, Aprenentatge Servei (ApS) de Desenvolupament Sostenible, Posidonia Green Project, SurfStainable